

The musicality of sounding objects. An ethnomusicological perspective on the study of musicality

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Abstract

Musicality is commonly defined as a set of abilities regarding the perception, appreciation and production of music. Studies on musicality tie this phenomenon to music without, however, providing an all-encompassing and unambiguous definition of what music is considered to be. The concept of music is complex to pin down as it changes across time and cultures and embraces a vast and often contrasting array of phenomena. I argue that studies on musicality may lend an incomplete picture of the subject by not fully defining its scope of action. My research on Calabrian sounding objects brought to light individuals who demonstrate the abilities commonly attributed to musicality but outside a musical context. These individuals defy the current definition of musicality, especially challenging its strong association with music. The article discusses Calabrian sounding objects and the refined musical abilities of people who make sound with these devices. It brings into the picture individuals who show refined abilities with sound, providing substantial evidence that the skills attributed to musicality are not necessarily linked to music. Drawing on extensive ethnographic data, this paper provides an ethnomusicological perspective on the study of musicality and calls for a new and more encompassing definition, one that is not bound to a specific definition of music.

***La musicalità degli oggetti sonori. Una prospettiva etnomusicologica sullo studio della musicalità.** La musicalità è comunemente definita come un insieme di capacità riguardanti la percezione, l'apprezzamento e la produzione di musica. Gli studi sulla musicalità legano questo fenomeno alla musica senza, tuttavia, fornire una definizione chiara e onnicomprensiva di cosa si intenda col termine musica. Il concetto di musica è difficile da determinare poiché varia nel tempo e in relazione agli orizzonti culturali e comprende un vasta gamma di fenomeni. Non*

definendo appropriatamente il proprio ambito d'indagine, gli studi sulla musicalità potrebbero fornire una visione incompleta del problema. La mia ricerca sugli oggetti sonori della tradizione calabrese ha portato alla luce individui che dimostrano di possedere le capacità normalmente attribuite alla musicalità anche se agiscono in contesti estranei al fare musica. Tali individui sfuggono alla definizione corrente di musicalità, sfidando in particolare il suo legame indissolubile con la musica. Questo articolo discute gli oggetti sonori della Calabria e le sviluppatissime abilità musicali dimostrate da coloro che usano tali dispositivi. Discute di individui che mostrano abilità raffinatissime concernenti il suono, fornendo prove sostanziali che le capacità attribuite alla musicalità non sono necessariamente legate alla musica. Attraverso una indagine etnografica approfondita, questo articolo fornisce una prospettiva etnomusicologica sullo studio della musicalità e invoca la necessità di una definizione più ampia del fenomeno che non sia legata ad una specifica definizione di musica.

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Introduction

Calabria is well known in Italian ethnomusicology through extensive documentation of its rich and diversified folk music (Ricci and Tucci 2004; 2007), its wide variety of traditional musical instruments (Cravero 2006; La Vena 2002; 2003; 2005; Leydi and Guizzi 1986; Staiti 2021), its soundscapes and its sounding objects (La Vena 1996; 2001; Ricci 2012). Research on Calabrian sounding objects focuses on a variety of devices that produce sound, including “minor” musical instruments, meaning instruments that do not hold the social status and artistic prestige of a “major” instrument such as the bagpipes or the diatonic accordion (*organetto*); toy musical instruments; objects whose primary function is solely to produce sound; and objects that are re-functionalised to make sound. These devices have various functions: some are used in religious or secular rituals; some are used to participate in music-making as a complement to a major musical instrument; and others are used just for making sound, for signalling or in leisure activity. Sounding objects have been thoroughly studied for their sonic and cultural value, for their role in various rituals in the region and from an organological standpoint.

Sound holds great importance in Calabria and is used in rituals and in everyday life. Antonello Ricci (2012) describes how sound is profoundly embedded in the Calabrian

community of Mesoraca and contributes to shaping the relationship between various human, non-human and supernatural agents. Vincenzo la Vena (1996; 2001) researches and classifies “minor” and toy instruments, as well as other sound-producing objects, in Terranova da Sibari. His collection and publications form, to date, the most complete organological study on this topic available in the region. Expanding on these studies, my article reflects on the possible contribution of Calabrian sounding objects to broadening our understanding of musicality.

I have researched the use of sounding objects in various communities scattered across the region, with a majority of informants coming from the central Tyrrhenian part of Calabria. Living in the area made it easier for me to gain the informants’ trust, which was necessary for acquiring data on this topic. My relationship with some of the informants predates the current research, while others were reached out through common acquaintances. Being known within the community as a bagpiper and as a person who is keen to learn about the local sound and music, my engagement with the informants goes beyond academic research and extends to musical performance and the transmission of crafts. Data were generated through participant observation and unstructured ethnographic interviews that frequently took the form of conversations. The data discussed in this paper include information generated in interviews with about 15 informants and in everyday interactions with an unspecified number of neighbours and acquaintances. The interviews focused on the individuals’ use and understanding of sound and sounding objects in relation to devices used both in rituals and in everyday life. I have researched how and why these objects are used, as well as the individuals’ understanding of their sonic, symbolic and cultural qualities. Most of the informants were men, although it was possible to find some female informants who remembered or discussed playing sounding objects. The gender disparity apparently derived from the different games played by boys and girls in the past. Furthermore, girls were more socially oriented towards domestic activities, whereas boys had a more active public life. Most of the informants presented in this paper are non-musicians, meaning people who have not played a musical instrument (whether a Western or a traditional one) and are not considered musicians in their community. The data generated through interviews and conversations were revised and discussed with the informants in an attempt to abide by Feld’s “dialogic editing” method (Feld 2012).

People who use sounding objects show refined musical abilities, which are expressed through making sound rather than making music. Showing productive abilities as well, these individuals challenge the current, widely adopted definition of musicality, especially its restriction to a musical field and the distinction often made between musicians and non-musicians. Drawing on extensive ethnographic data, this article examines the musicality embedded in making sound and demonstrates how sounding objects cross and overlap with music at different levels. The aim is not to assimilate sound and music but to demonstrate that a similar if not identical type of musicality is at play in musicians

and in sound-making non-musicians. Musicality is therefore expressed through sound or music depending on the individual's personal and social development.

I will first discuss what I believe to be the limits of the current research on musicality and will attempt a possible, more encompassing definition of musicality. I will then discuss my ethnographic data and demonstrate crossing and overlapping between making sound using sounding objects and making music. In this section, I demonstrate how making sound and making music are more correlated than we usually think. I will then discuss the musical abilities of people who play sounding objects. I will show how such individuals possess refined aural, analytical, ecological and productive skills that are entirely pertinent to musicality.

Musicality and sound

Musicians are often defined by their expertise in playing an instrument: years of formal musical training are usually a marker of an individual's musicianship (Ericsson, Krampe, and Tesch-Römer 1993). Furthermore, «popular views often include a perception that [...] musicians are “born not made”» (Rickard and Chin 2017: 289). This view, often encouraged by Western musical training methods, fosters the idea that music is accessible only to a selected few. Such a definition is inadequate to describe the complex reality of musicianship, and recent studies on musicality have pointed out how people who do not perform music show various degrees of musical ability. The Merriam-Webster dictionary defines musicality as «sensitivity to, knowledge of, or talent for music», without specifying whether these qualities refer to music production or reception. More explicitly, the Macquarie dictionary defines musicianship as the «skill and sensitivity in performing or perception in appreciating music». Sloboda (2004) notes that there is both “productive” and “receptive” musical expertise. Sandra E. Trehub (2023: 1) writes that «musicality refers to the uniquely human constellation of skills underlying our ability to perceive, appreciate, and produce music». Researchers commonly attribute musicality not only to the production of music but also to its reception. «The reception of music involves conscious attending to sounds, and processing of musical information to make sense of what is heard» (Rickard and Chin 2017: 5). Recognising receptive musical abilities led many researchers to investigate musicality also in people who do not perform music. These individuals, commonly defined as non-musicians, have been increasingly included in studies on musicality. Non-musicians are attributed only receptive abilities, as opposed to musicians who are attributed both receptive and productive musical abilities. Müllensiefen *et al.* (2014) conducted a large-scale study on the musicality of non-musicians. The individuals they studied are recognised as possessing listening, perceptual, emotional and analytical abilities, as well as the capacity to engage emotionally, socially and spiritually with music. However, they seem to be considered unable to participate in the production of music in any form.

Rickard and Chin (2017: 7) highlight some limitations of the studies on musicality when they note that «the limited attention to non-performance musical engagement in research is compounded by an absence of methodology suitable for identifying the “musical non-musician”». The authors also note that «research on musicians routinely contrasts musicians with “non-musicians,” but reflecting the lack of agreement in definition of a musician, the criteria for selection are inconsistent» (*ibidem*: 4). I argue that the problem resides in the very same definition of musicality that these studies often adopt. The studies refer musicality to a never-expressed definition of music. Without an unequivocal definition of music there cannot be a definition of musicality. In that regard, Honing *et al.* (2015: 2) note that «definitional issues are especially problematic because there are no conventional defining criteria of music».

Ethnomusicology has extensively reflected on the concept of music and the importance of including non-musical sound in the scope of its study. Sound holds great importance in human societies and is the fundamental ingredient of music. F. Alberto Gallo (1986: 13) invites historians of Medieval music to extend their focus to «every sonic manifestation that may have had significance to people at that time».¹ Italian and, as far as the focus of this paper is concerned, Calabrian ethnomusicology has had a broad and long-lasting interest in sound and sound-producing devices (see, for instance, Bonanzinga 1992; Ghirardini 2020; La Vena 1996; 2001; Ricci 2012; 2016). When defining the object of his study in Mesoraca, Italian anthropologist Antonello Ricci makes no distinction between meaningful sound and music, both of which are associated with some level of formalisation. He writes (1996: 45): «Of key importance, but sometimes also particularly difficult, is to pinpoint where a certain culture places the line between what it defines as a sonic or “musical” event – that is, formalised so that it conveys a certain, precise meaning – and what is extraneous to that ambit». He also warns about the dangers of interpreting what pertains to music and what does not, when he writes: «Often, we the listeners and interpreters of a culture include phenomena in a specific category, sometimes for analytical convenience, other times for an ethnocentric stretch» (*ibidem*: 45).² Sergio Bonanzinga (1992) depicts blurred boundaries between phenomena pertaining to the realms of sound and music. In his study of non-musical sounds in Sicily, Bonanzinga shows how sound and music intersect quite easily at a sonic, aesthetic, functional, social, cultural and symbolic level. These studies, besides providing interesting insights into the difficulty of pinpointing the concept of music, dialogue with an international scholarship similarly reflecting on sound and music. Steven Feld delineates his anthropology of sound

¹ Original: «Lo storico della musica medievale dovrebbe estendere sistematicamente i suoi interessi ad ogni manifestazione sonora che abbia avuto un significato per gli uomini del tempo».

² Original: «Di centrale importanza, ma anche, a volte, di estrema difficoltà, è riuscire a individuare dove una determinata cultura ponga il confine tra ciò che essa definisce un fatto sonoro o “musicale” – vale a dire formalizzato in maniera da veicolare un certo, preciso significato – e ciò che è invece estraneo a tale ambito. Sovente siamo noi, ascoltatori e interpreti di una cultura, ad inglobare fenomeni in una certa categoria, a volte per comodità di analisi, altre volte per una forzatura etnocentrica.»

as a criticism of Merriam's lack of inclusion of sound in the study of anthropology. In his own words, Feld «tried to critique the limitations, sonic and cultural, imposed by the notion of “music”» (Feld and Brenneis 2004: 463). Also, Feld's further development of acoustemology (Feld 2015) is an attempt to include sounds that are outside of human control. These works show that musical and non-musical sounds are strictly correlated, as both types of sound equally contribute to our understanding of the world and convey social, cultural or ecological meaning.

Despite lacking a common definition of music, all studies on musicality test a similar set of abilities. Honing (2018: 52) identifies «potential candidates for the basic components of musicality that have been proposed in the recent literature», such as «relative pitch (e.g. contour and interval analysis), regularity and beat perception, tonal encoding of pitch, and metrical encoding of rhythm». Rickard and Chin (2017: 5) state that non-musicians «are able to efficiently discriminate, identify and predict key features and structures in music, categorize melodic sequences that are similar and different, apply segmentation rules to unfamiliar sequences, recall melodies on the basis of global features and identify intended emotions in a piece». Trehub (2023) tests infants' ability to identify relevant pitch and timing differences in musical sequences, or their ability to memorise and recognise melodies. Müllensiefen *et al.* (2014) identify their subjects' perceptual and singing abilities (e.g. to judge others' singing ability, compare performances, demonstrate their own tonal perception, sing back after hearing 2-3 times, sing or play from memory, sing back hours later) and their emotional abilities related to listening and producing music. This may not be an exhaustive list of all the ingredients of musicality, but it defines a clear set of features that apply across different possible definitions of music. Some of these abilities also show the limitations of the definition of musicality that I pointed out earlier. For instance, when testing skills such as «regularity and beat perception, tonal encoding of pitch, and metrical encoding of rhythm», the researchers implicitly limit their analysis of musicality to a very specific type of music that is regular, measured or tonal. Thus, they exclude a vast array of music that does not show these characteristics. Researching musicality in such a restricted and often not well-defined musical field may provide an incomplete picture of the problem. I argue that the “basic components” of musicality can be summarised as ways of making sense of sound and (more or less complex) sonic structures, whether musical or not. Indeed, pitch contour, intervallic relationships, temporal and rhythmic structures, emotional and symbolic associations and the other components tested in studies on musicality are common features of non-musical sound. Bird calls feature all these components without belonging to the realm of human music: they have rhythmic structures and pitch relationships that can be decoded and reproduced by human listeners, and elicit emotional, ecological and symbolic responses. In my view, musicality seems to pertain to the ability to make sense, in reception and production, of what we hear, and it does not manifest itself exclusively in relation to music. I think that investigating musicality beyond a restricted musical realm will lend a more encompassing

and complete picture of the problem. The informants in my research show all the abilities commonly attributed to musicality regardless of a musical context. In the next section, I will discuss various points of overlap between making sound through sounding objects and making music. The aim is to demonstrate how non-musical sound is closely related to music and cannot be excluded from the investigation of musicality.

Sounding objects: their contacts and overlap with music

When reflecting on the categories of sound and music, one is faced with an interesting terminological and possibly epistemological issue in Calabria. The term used by older generations to describe what is commonly understood as making music is *sunare* (or *sonare*), which literally translates as *sounding, to make sound*. Indeed, *sunare* is used unconditionally when referring both to the act of producing sound and to playing music. A traditional musician is usually called a *sonature*. The Italian term *musica* is also present, and it is often used as a qualifier rather than an object. In fact, *sunare a musica*, which could be translated as “playing à la music” or “playing in the style of music”, is the common expression used to describe a person’s ability to play repertoires outside the local folk music, or to read a score. This use of *musica* appears to define something that is to some extent extraneous to the local culture or that is acquired from outside. The distinction seems to point towards different ways of categorising the sonic events: one pertains traditionally to sounding and includes both playing folk music and making sound; the other refers to something acquired from outside and includes non-traditional repertoires and the ability to read sheet music. It is important to point out that using the same term *sunare* for making music with the bagpipes and producing sound with a leaf does not speak of an equivalence between the two phenomena, which are clearly conceptualised differently in the local culture. Nevertheless, using *sunare* for both activities seems to put playing the bagpipes somewhat closer to making sound than to playing “*a musica*”, at least terminologically if not epistemologically. Noticing this proximity is important because, as I will show in the following paragraphs, the acts of producing sound and making music cross at various levels and seem to rely on similar sets of skills.

Sounding objects were commonly used as toys in the childhood of those who are now over 65 years old, although I was able to find a few younger informants. Almost everybody in that age group was able to mention some sound-producing toys or instruments that they used to play as children. The most commonly mentioned sounding devices are the overtone flute made with the chestnut bark, known as *frischettara*³ (also called *vischetta*

³ Overtone flute made with fresh chestnut bark. A straight stalk is cut a few tens of centimetres long. The wood is removed to obtain a hollow tube of fresh bark. One end of the tube is cut transverse, and a window is opened a few centimetres away. The performer uses his tongue as a block and fingers the opposite end of the tube to modulate the pitch.

FIGURE 1. A *pipita* made with a wild oat stalk (on the left) and a *viscarualu* (on the right).

or *frischetta*); the *pipite*,⁴ single-idioglottal reeds like those used in the local bagpipes; and various types of block flutes called *viscaruali* (also *vischiatti* or *frischietti*)⁵ (Fig. 1).

Until the relatively recent past, it was common for people from small villages and rural communities – such as shepherds, farmers and artisans – to make many of the things they needed by hand. Similarly, sounding objects were for the most part homemade: children would commonly make their own devices in response to their need to play. Many informants affirm that playing with sounding objects was dictated by poverty and the consequent lack of toys. The knowledge of how to make instruments and sounding objects was passed on in the social context, through exchange between peers of the same age and across generations. Many informants report that they had learnt the skills to make and play sounding objects from other children. The more complex instruments, such as flutes, single clarinets and double clarinets, were commonly learnt either from older peers or from relatives in intergenerational exchange. The use of sounding objects went along with a craftsmanship and an empirical knowledge of the materials involved

⁴ Single idioglottal reed. The instruments are made with a seasoned tube of wild cane (*Arundo donax*) and with a fresh wild oat stalk (*Avena fatua*). A lamella a few centimetres long is opened from the top down, near the upper node. The lower node is removed to leave the tube ending open. The entire length of the lamella is placed in the performer's mouth.

⁵ Block flutes made with a tube of seasoned giant cane (*Arundo donax*). The block is made with a piece of softwood (commonly fig or pear). The instruments observed commonly have four fingerholes and one thumbhole.

in their construction. These practical skills were applied not only to making sound-producing devices but also to making everyday objects and other toys. Enrico Ruperto⁶ recalls how, as a young shepherd, he would engage in manual activities as a “pastime”. During long days in the fields, he would build wooden plough models and make wild oat reeds, apparently making no distinction between the two activities. Although not all homemade toys were intended primarily to produce sound, the impressive number of sounding objects that were made to play with speaks of the high value attributed to sound in that culture and society. It is particularly telling that satisfying a recreational need would extensively involve making sound. This need for sound combined with the need for making music and dancing that has emerged multiple times in research in the area. Ferlaino (2017) writes that people would make music and dance all night despite poverty, hunger, and the fatigue caused by long and exhausting workdays. Similarly, the informants describe how this need for making music and dance was satisfied even in the absence of musicians who could play for dancers. Teresa Vaccaro⁷ says that, during breaks from picking olives, she and her peers would elect someone to imitate the *organetto* or the bagpipes with their voice so that the others could dance.

The closeness between making music and using sounding objects is revealed in the words of many informants, who played sounding objects because it was impossible for them to access a musical instrument. Secondo Mancini⁸ repeatedly affirms that they would play with these devices as children because they had no musical instruments. Similarly, Antonio Vescio⁹ justifies the use of sounding objects in his childhood as a consequence of his lack of access to *zampogna* or *organetto*. Eugenio Curcio¹⁰ explicitly attributes his childhood use of sounding objects to the impossibility of accessing a major musical instrument. This information points to the use of sounding objects as a response to the children’s desire to access the musical world of adults. Lacking the chance to access a musical instrument, the children satisfied their desire using less complex and more readily available devices. This hypothesis is corroborated by the children’s attempt to imitate the visual aesthetics of musical instruments on their sounding devices. Children used pyrographies to embellish some of their instruments, even the more rudimentary ones. Cesare Macchione¹¹ affirms that children would embellish the *trummetta ‘e canna*¹²

⁶ Study of Calabrian Sounding Objects. Field Notes - E. Ruperto: <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10260256>>.

⁷ Study of Calabrian Sounding Objects. Interview and Field Notes - A. Trunzo, S. Trunzo and T. Vaccaro: <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10256961>>.

⁸ Study of Calabrian Sounding Objects. Field Notes - S. Mancini: <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10259904>>.

⁹ Study of Calabrian Sounding Objects. Interview and Field Notes - A. Vescio & G. Lucia: <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10257058>>.

¹⁰ Study of Calabrian Sounding Objects. Interview and Field Notes - E. Curcio: <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10257148>>.

¹¹ Study of Calabrian Sounding Objects. Interview and Field Notes - C. Macchione: <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10257100>>.

¹² Tubular reed. An internode of seasoned giant cane (*Arundo donax*) is cut, preserving the upper node.

(Video 1) with similar patterns to those normally applied by adults to flutes and double clarinets, which in turn imitate to some extent the carvings used to embellish bagpipe bodies. Making sound could be interpreted as a first step into the sound world of the adults. Playing with sounding objects constituted the children's musical realm, a fundamental phase during which children would experiment with the acoustics and aesthetics of sound and acquire empirical knowledge in sound production that would be fundamental to their possible future development as musicians. Children playing with sounding objects could be likened to people making scale models in order to learn woodworking. Eugenio Curcio used to build scale model furniture to get acquainted and experiment with shapes and materials, as he wanted to undertake an apprenticeship as a carpenter. In a similar way, making sound and sounding objects could be seen as a miniature version of the musical world of adults, a fundamental phase in the person's musical development.

The following information expands on and corroborates the previous considerations. Some devices were explicitly used as propaedeutic instruments for learning the bagpipes. Such is the case for double clarinets (*pipite* or *zampugnedde*)¹³ and cane flutes, which were the inexpensive entry point to learning the repertoire and technical aspects of the bagpipes before a person was able to afford the real instrument (Fig. 2). All the informants in this research cite flutes and double clarinets as toys with which they played in their childhood, although almost none of them have become bagpipers.

Through double clarinets, one would acquire theoretical and empirical knowledge of the materials, their acoustic properties and the techniques of sound production, learn to make reeds, and eventually assimilate the repertoire of the *zampogna*. This practice, documented in Ferlaino (2017) and La Vena (2009), has also emerged in this research. Bagpiper Santo Trunzo¹⁴ still has the double clarinet that Giovanni Carpino gave him over sixty years ago and which he played extensively in his youth and still plays occasionally. Being more complex instruments, flutes and double clarinets were normally learnt from older peers. These devices seem to constitute a further step in the musical development of the person, a more advanced access point to the musical world of adults. Some sounding objects are explicitly used to make music. Such is the case for devices such as spoons¹⁵ or the bottle struck with a key,¹⁶ which are sometimes used to participate in

A slit is opened from the node down with a sharp knife for a few centimetres. The instrument is activated by blowing from the open end of the pipe.

¹³ Two internodes of seasoned giant cane (*Arundo donax*) are cut preserving the upper node. A simple idioglottal reed similar to the *pipita* is cut from the top down on both pipes. The right-hand chanter has four fingerholes. The left-hand chanter has 3 fingerholes and the lower end of the pipe is cut diagonally so that it can be fingered with the little finger. The performer puts the entire length of both reeds in the mouth.

¹⁴ Study of Calabrian Sounding Objects. Field Notes - S. Trunzo: <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10259892>>.

¹⁵ A pair of metal spoons is held with the convex parts of the spoons touching each other in one hand. The concave side of the spoons is hit against the palm of the other hand, letting the heads of the spoons strike against each other.

¹⁶ A glass bottle is struck with a door key. The bottle is held in one hand while its bottom is laid against the body of the performer. The key is held in the other hand, with the thumb on one end and the middle

FIGURE 2. Double clarinet with pyrographies made by Santo Trunzo.

music-making. Spoons and a bottle struck with a key are sometimes repurposed to serve as percussion instruments and to accompany the leading bagpipes or *organetto*. Giovanni De Paola¹⁷ uses a pair of metal spoons to participate in music-making. He learnt to play spoons as a child because he could not afford to learn the bagpipes or *organetto*. In Video 2, spoons and a bottle struck with a modified door handle accompany the *zampogna a chiave* during the Festa della Pita in Alessandria del Carretto.

The fact that some players of sounding objects fall back on such devices because it is impossible for them to acquire and perform a major musical instrument is particularly telling. Noteworthy is the case of Giuseppe Rusciano, whom I met at the Festa della Pita. Rusciano wanted to play *organetto* as a child but did not have the resources to buy and learn one. As an adult, he bought what he calls the *nacchere*¹⁸ in order to participate in music-making. Interestingly, this idiophone, made with a series of wooden slats, looks extraordinarily like an *organetto* (Fig. 3). Also, the way of holding it and the playing technique resemble those of the diatonic accordion. These individuals did not undertake

finger on the other and it is struck perpendicularly against the bottle's body.

¹⁷ Giovanni de Paola, Giuseppe Rusciano and Giovanni Cristiano's data are accessible at the following link <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10257707>>.

¹⁸ A series of wooden slats are tied parallel to each other from the top, separated by small blocks of wood. Two leather hand straps are placed at the two ends. A shoulder leather strap is used to hold the instrument. The instrument is activated by moving the hands so that the slats hit against each other. This instrument is also called *tric trac*.

Photo: Christian Ferlaino

FIGURE 3. The *nacchere*.

the path to musicianship, which in Calabria means to learn a major instrument such as the *organetto* or the bagpipes, for economic reasons. Although the spoons, bottle and *nacchere* do not possess the social and artistic status attributed to bagpipes, accordions or frame drums, they allow individuals such as De Paola and Rusciano to participate in musical activities. They allow non-trained individuals to contribute creatively and socially to making music in their communities. It is also worth noting that they act in a musical context where participation, regardless of skill, is widely accepted. Musical professionalism is a relatively recent phenomenon in Calabria, where most of the musical activity (including when it involves proficient musicians) is done in the community with a participatory approach. In these settings, non-musicians contribute to the musical outcome in whatever way they can, by clapping, shouting or playing minor instruments.

Sounding objects are used not only by non-trained individuals: expert musicians keep playing these instruments throughout their lives too. Bagpipers commonly use double clarinets and flutes in their domestic (non-public) musical activity (see for instance Ferlaino 2017). In these cases, using sounding objects perfectly overlaps with music-making, clearly exposing further closeness between the two activities. Both expert musicians and non-musicians use sound devices to experiment with sound. Bagpiper Santo Trunzo showed me a clarinet with applied idioglottal reed and two fingerholes (Fig. 4), quite an uncommon construction for his place of origin, where clarinets normally have integral

FIGURE 4. Santo Trunzo's recycled clarinet.

idioglottal reeds and four fingerholes. Trunzo made this instrument from a clarinet, the upper part of which, including the reed and two holes, had broken. He recycled the intact segment and applied a reed to it. Although Trunzo attributes no importance to this device, it is telling that he keeps and plays the broken instrument. This attitude speaks of a need to experiment with sound, which is anything but unimportant.

Similar experimentation with sound and material through sounding objects is also found among non-musicians. Even the simpler sounding objects reveal great ingenuity. These devices reveal an approach to material that is driven by a strong desire to produce sound. Materials seem to have undergone a true exploration of their acoustic properties in the individual's search for suitable ways to produce sound. The *trummetta 'e lauru*¹⁹ is a good example (Video 3). Despite being a rudimentary device, its construction entails a profound understanding of the way reeds work and reveals a strong wish on the part of the player to experiment with materials in search of effective ways to produce sound. The profound knowledge of the materials used in construction and the drive to produce sound can also be observed in the *trummetta 'e cipudda*²⁰ (Video 4). Many informants

¹⁹ Ribbon reed made with a bay leaf framed in a slit bay stalk. A piece of bay stalk is cut longitudinally for a few centimeters at one end. A bay leaf is inserted in the slit and cut into shape.

²⁰ The fresh onion leaf is a tall, green cone with thick, meaty walls that stands up straight. It is cut from

remember this object being made for them as children by a female relative in the household. Angela Trunzo still makes it for her grandchildren. It is interesting to note that the instrument is made from an edible plant, and its construction involves cooking the leaf. Women were socially oriented towards domestic activities, an important one of which was making food. The edible plant-derived instrument could be read as a by-product of this gendered activity. Women, who were used to handling plants for food-making, mastered the materials needed for this activity, which in this case also involved knowledge of the onion leaf's acoustic properties.

An overlap between sound and music can be found in the way both are utilised in the private sphere. Making music is traditionally an activity that is executed in social contexts and normally entails a strong social component. Traditional musicians are recognised in their communities both for their skills and for their musical activity within the community. The strong link between sociality and music also emerges from the fact that many musicians stop playing their instruments when the social occasions are lost. Sound and music in the private sphere are practised as a leisure activity – a “pastime” in the words of almost every informant. Both music and sound-making are ways of expressing oneself through sound. In the private sphere, musicians and users of sounding objects fulfil their need for leisure and find delight in producing sound.

The musicality of sounding objects

In the previous section, I have demonstrated similarities and points of overlap between making music and playing with sounding objects. Although the two activities are not equivalent in the local culture, it is possible to observe significant closeness in the way many of these devices are used as an access point to the musical world, whether for making sound for its own sake, for training or explicitly for making music. I will now demonstrate how individuals who play sounding objects show that they possess the abilities normally attributed to musicality, including the production abilities that are normally reserved for musicians. These skills and abilities are not expressed in a musical context, which renders the current definition of musicality inadequate to fully describe the complexity of the phenomena at play.

Many of the informants are not musicians and did not undertake the training to become one. Nevertheless, they are able to talk about technical aspects of sound production, including the acoustic responses of materials and spaces. The informants know the different acoustic responses of various types of wood and other materials. They know where to find the most suitable cane, when is the best time of the year to cut it, and how to cure and work it in order to properly produce sound. They have preferred materials and

the base and heated with fire to make it wilt. The pointed end of the leaf is removed. The performer blows from the bottom end while the narrow opening at the top works as a double reed.

working methods that are better suited to express their idea of sound. Thus, these individuals make technical and aesthetic judgements when they construct or play a sounding object. Informants also make technical judgements concerning the simplest of devices, such as a blade of grass. Giuseppe Guidoccio²¹ talks about how the rigidity, thickness and dimensions of the leaf influence the sonic result. Similarly, Eugenio Curcio discusses the acoustic response of different leaves. Giovanni de Paola and Giovanni Cristiano speak of the best-sounding bottles to be struck with the key. They discuss which water and soft-drink glass bottles are best suited for playing and which produce the brightest and most carrying sound.²² Such examples reveal that these individuals possess empirical knowledge of the acoustic responses of different materials and an understanding of sound-production principles. They also show that they possess a clear image of the sound they are after, which is driven by well-defined aesthetic considerations.

The informants often make social and ecological judgements regarding sound. Through sounding objects, they establish a network of relationships with the environment and the community. Giuseppe Orlando²³ summarises many of these aspects when he talks about his childhood experience with playing the *trocca*²⁴ (Fig. 5). He says that children used to fight to play this instrument, which speaks of the social status that children attributed to playing it. He also speaks of the changed social positioning of the children within the community's rituals when he affirms that nowadays children are almost ashamed to play this instrument. Orlando also makes acoustic and ecological considerations when he talks about the places he most liked to play the *trocca* because of the way it resonated more pleasurably. His favourite spot was a rock in the old town in Nocera Terinese, from which the sound would diffuse over the whole west side of the town and reflect back from the mountain that stands opposite the valley. This recollection reveals Orlando's ability to differentiate the ways in which the instrument resonates and to appreciate the acoustic responses of different spaces. It also reveals a way of attributing ecological meaning to sound, which mediates his relationship with the urban and natural space.

Attributing ecological meaning to sound is another trait of musicality. Man-made sound often seems related to natural sound, and bird calls seem to be the most obvious example. During the Pita, a man walked about whistling a bird call (Audio 1). Giuseppe Guidoccio imitates the rooster's crowing with a blade of grass (Video 5). Similarly, he

²¹ Study of Calabrian Sounding Objects. Interview and Field Notes - G. Guidoccio: <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10259772>>.

²² Sounding objects are mostly made of natural materials available in the surroundings of the makers' communities. Makers also use recycled materials, which are readily available and durable and possess properties that are not easily found in natural materials (e.g., the flexibility and stretchability of gum and plastic). Examples include bird calls that feature membranes recycled from old rubber gloves or balloons and toy telephones made with tin cans instead of cane and leather.

²³ Study of Calabrian Sounding Objects. Field Notes - G. Orlando: <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10259851>>.

²⁴ This idiophone is used during the rituals of the Holy Week. It is a wooden slab with metallic beaters hinged on either side. The instrument is activated by quickly rotating the slab back and forth along its vertical axis.

FIGURE 5. *Trocca*.

seems to imitate a bird call with the *pipita* (single reed). Domenico Mastroianni²⁵ likened the sound produced with the *trummetta 'e cipudda* to the hen's cackle. Cesare Macchione imitates a bird call with a blade of grass (Video 6). Eugenio Curcio calls the percussion instrument made with a half walnut shell *cicala*²⁶ because the ticking sound that this instrument produces resembles the calling song of the insect (Fig. 6). For people who spend much of their time outdoors – such as shepherds and farmers – it is plausible that natural sound constitutes a primary reference.

Sound is used to socialise similarly to music. The social aspects of making sound are commonly addressed in the interviews. Giovanbattista Vaccaro²⁷ and Cesare Macchione say that children would make sounding objects and play together in company. They also used to compete to make the best sound-producing objects. This information

²⁵ Study of Calabrian Sounding Objects. Field Notes - D. Mastroianni: <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10263222>>.

²⁶ The *cicala* is a small percussion instrument made with a half walnut shell. A thread is wound around the shell and used to spring-load a toothpick or a small piece of cane. The instrument is activated by lifting the toothpick with the fingers and letting it fall back to strike the shell.

²⁷ Study of Calabrian Sounding Objects. Interview and Field Notes - G. Vaccaro: <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10257733>>.

FIGURA 6. *Cicala*.

demonstrates the social aspects embedded in making sound and the technical abilities required for the construction and use of these devices. Children would gain and exchange knowledge by constructing instruments, learning how to make a louder instrument or one that allowed them to play longer sounds than others. All these abilities entail knowledge of the materials and construction methods as well as developed technical skills. The social component is also evident in the various rituals in which sound plays a central role. Sound and sounding objects are an integral part of rituals throughout the year, and have a special place in the Carnival, Lent and Easter celebrations across the whole region. *Trocca* and noisemakers shape the soundscape of almost every community during the Easter Triduum. During *Jam'a scuntrè Marz* in Villapiana, people parade the streets making noise on the last day of February to welcome March. In the Good Friday procession of the *Cordata* in Diamante, members of the fishermen's brotherhood play the huge *tocche tocche*²⁸ (Video 7). In these rituals, sound is charged with symbolic and spiritual connotations and with personal and social significance.

²⁸ This is a wooden box to which spring-loaded wooden hammers are attached. A rotating axle raises the hammers and lets them beat against the sounding board. The instrument is activated by rotating a crank which turns the axle.

Sound is also used to communicate or convey meaning. Shepherds use calls and whistles to communicate and interact with the herds. They also use bells for herd animals, through which they establish a complex network of signification with various human and non-human agents (Ricci 2012; 2016). Battista Vaccaro says that children used the sound of the *trummetta 'e cucuzza*²⁹ to mock someone (Video 8). This instrument produces a raucous and pig-like honking like a raspberry, another sound widely used in Italy for mockery. The attribution of meaning to sound also emerged in a saying that a farmer used to express the concept “unity is strength”: he translated the concept with the phrase “one walnut makes no sound”. All these examples demonstrate that individuals are able to attribute strong social, cultural, relational and symbolic significance to sound, abilities that are also tested in studies on musicality. In addition, these individuals demonstrate productive abilities when they use sound actively to express themselves and relate with the surrounding world.

The productive musical abilities that emerge in making sound are mostly evident in the capacity of the informants to imitate complex sounds. In (Video 5), Giuseppe Guidoccio imitates the rooster’s crowing with a blade of grass. In that clip, it is possible to recognise many ingredients of musicality at once. In fact, Guidoccio demonstrates that he has correctly decoded and memorised the pitch, interval and temporal profile of the rooster’s crow. He has also reproduced it in great detail, choosing a device – the blade of grass – that best matches the timbre of the original sound. Guidoccio demonstrates that he possesses both receptive and productive musical abilities, although these are not expressed through music. He also says that in his youth he was able to imitate an owl’s call by whistling with cupped hands. His imitation was so good that the bird would respond to his calls. This type of mimetic ability can be observed in various individuals in non-musical contexts and reveals the refined musicality involved in making sound. These skills also manifest themselves when the informants imitate the sound of these instruments to describe them or when they imitate a piece of music with words. When Angela Trunzo imitates the sound of the *trummetta 'e cipudda*, her singing matches the timbre and the rhythmic irregularity of the device’s sound (Audio 2). Teresa Vaccaro imitates the *sonate* (pieces of music) for *organetto* (Audio 3) and *zampogna* (Audio 4), to which she would dance in the absence of a musician. Hunters say that birds responded to their calls, which demonstrates refined musical skills in discerning and imitating gendered sounds so as to attract specimens of the desired sex. Mimesis entails the ability to receive, decode and reproduce all the aspects of a sonic event. In order to imitate a sound, informants have to be able to discern and reproduce its melodic profile, its sequence of intervals, its temporal and rhythmic structure and its timbre – which is probably the most overlooked “musical” feature in studies on musicality.

²⁹ This is a tubular reed instrument made with the fresh stalk of the pumpkin leaf. The leaf is removed to leave the upper node closed. A top-down cut a few centimeters long is made from the node to obtain the reeds. The instrument is activated by putting the entire length of the reed in the mouth and blowing.

Bells for herd animals are a striking example of the personal, social, ecological, aesthetic and symbolic signification of sound and opens a window on more-than-human musicality. Bells are functional devices used to keep track of the flock at a distance and single out animals in a herd. The bell's sound conveys information about the animals' activity, their position in space and the type of terrain they move on. Shepherds perceive their flock as producing a single sound, a unique sonic entity that must produce a pleasurable harmony, which is often the subject of appreciation and comments within the community. The flocks' sound becomes a marker of the shepherd's identity through which they self-identify and are recognised within the community. The various bell sounds are attributed to the animals according to their role, social status and personality, therefore, conveying knowledge about animals' individual and social traits (Ricci 2012; 2016; Ferlaino 2023). In the ethnographic data emerges also that bells convey social meaning among the animals: shepherds say that the animals recognise each other and interact through their bells' sounds, thus attributing them sonic agency. Bells also convey symbolic meaning: some shepherds do not use bells during Lent and put them on the animals on Easter morning when the resounding church bells symbolise the resurrection of Christ.

The examples discussed in this paper demonstrate that those who use sounding objects possess refined skills and abilities regarding sound that pertain entirely to musicality. The informants reveal a profound understanding of the acoustics, aesthetics and technical aspects of these devices. They also attribute sonic, social, cultural, symbolic and relational significance to sound, abilities that are also tested in studies on musicality. Most importantly, these individuals also show productive abilities that are normally attributed only to musicians. They use sound in an expressive way and show various levels of music production ability that manifest through making sound rather than music.

Conclusion

In this paper, I have demonstrated different levels of overlap between producing sound and making music. Playing sounding objects seems to constitute the "musical" world of children, an initial step into music-making that is achieved by using the means available at that age and in that social position. Children's desire to make music is expressed through shared and readily available knowledge about sonic devices. At this stage, children experiment with sound and refine their technical abilities regarding sound production and the visual elements of adult musical instruments. This initial step then grants access to more complex sounding devices that are specifically intended as propaedeutic to the bagpipes. Many stay at the stage of making sound, whereas some keep developing their musical skills and access traditional musical instruments. Sounding objects also allow people to participate in music-making, taking advantage of a participative approach embedded in local musical practice. In these cases, people fall back on sounding objects because it is

impossible for them to learn the bagpipes or *organetto* due to social or economic impediments. The devices allow non-musicians to directly participate in musical activity. For those who keep using sounding objects throughout their lives, making sound is a leisure activity, a way of expressing oneself through sound similar to making music. The sound of these devices also has an ecological component that allows people to establish relationships with the environment and dialogue with the surrounding natural soundscape. Sounding objects are also a place for experimentation for musicians and non-musicians, who use them throughout their lives. Producers of sound are able to make aesthetic judgements, understand the acoustic response of materials and places, and discern the social and symbolic significance of sound. They are capable of moulding the sonic matter in order to project their idea of sound. They demonstrate the ability to perceive, understand, decode and reproduce the various features of different sonic structures. They also attribute meaning and link emotions to both received and produced sound.

Mimesis and the other skills and abilities of decoding and producing extra-musical sound discussed in this article fall perfectly under the definition of musicality. The unorthodox instruments discussed in this paper allow people to express themselves through sound on an imaginative, perceptual, relational or improvisatory level. They initiate a creative exploration of the mimetic potential of sound, which might be considered a precursor to music. I do not intend to equate making sound to making music. Rather, I maintain that the musicality involved in making sound is the same as that involved in making music. Both activities are structured socially and culturally and rely on a profound understanding of the materials and their acoustic properties; both rely on the ability to discern, imitate and reproduce sound; both allow individuals to express social, relational, emotional, symbolic and ecological needs through sound. These skills and abilities are then expressed through sound or music, depending on the individual's personal and social development.

The examples discussed in this paper call for the inclusion of producers of sound at any level in the study of musicality, further challenging the distinction between musicians and non-musicians. Currently, people who produce sound are generally not included in studies on musicality. These individuals may constitute a category on their own and probably render the distinction between musicians and non-musicians less than adequate. As they do not perform music, they do not fully belong to the category of musicians; however, as they show refined production skills, the category of non-musicians is also not entirely fitting.

The fact that the abilities ascribed to musicality also manifest themselves in non-musical contexts, as discussed in this paper, calls for a more encompassing definition of musicality, one that is not bound to a specific definition of music. In my view, musicality concerns the skills and abilities involved in decoding, interpreting and producing (less or more complex) sound. One might challenge this definition by saying that the skills regarding sound are not musical but rather merely auditory. However, the sounds discussed in this paper are not solely acoustic or auditory phenomena because even the simplest of

these sounds conveys cultural, social and symbolic knowledge. Rickard and Chin (2017: 12) write that «musicianship is also about the things and attitudes that music embraces, and not just about producing music». Sound, whether musical or not, is a way of knowing the world (Feld 2015). As I have discussed in this paper, it embraces similar “things and attitudes” to those of music, thus calling for its inclusion in studies on musicality. A more encompassing definition of musicality that includes sound in any form, could also be beneficial to comprehend musicality in more-than-human agents – e.g. for biomusicology studies which investigate the biological basis of musicality across species (Fitch 2015; Hoeschele *et al.* 2015). Duengen *et al.* reflect on the limits of applying human categories to non-human agents and «highlight the abundance of interesting features found in nonhuman animal sound production» hoping «to find this broader perspective in more research» (Duengen, Sarfati, & Ravignani 2023, 81). Including sound in studies on musicality will contribute to untie musicality from a predominantly human concept of music and lend a more complete picture of the phenomenon.

Video Contents

Audio Contents

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